

IN-HABIT – Inclusive Health And wellBeing In small and medium size ciTies

D8.4 CITY COMMUNICATION PACK

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VERSION HISTORY

Version	Status	Date	Contributor/partner	Summary of changes
V 0.1	Draft	16/12/2021	D. Bavuso, C. Marrone, S. Marrone (BOT)	Advanced draft
V 0.2	Advanced draft	20/12/2021	LCREA, UCO	Peer Reviewed
V 0.3	Final document	21/12/2021	BOT	Feedback included, language final revision

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

CA	Consortium Agreement
DECO	Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication & Outreach
DC	Dissemination & Communication
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GDEI	Gender, Diversity, Equity, Inclusion
H2020	Horizon 2020 projects
IHW	Inclusive Health and Wellbeing
KLC	Key Local Contact
LCA	Local Community Activator
PC	Project Coordinator
PP	Project Partner
RTD	Research, technology and development
SMSCs	Small and medium sized cities

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WP

Work Package

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PARTNERS' SHORT NAMES

AVUE	Neighbourhood Association of Las Palmeras
BOT	Book on a Tree
BSC	Baltic Studies Centre
B4B	Bridge for Billions
CORD	Ayuntamiento de Córdoba
DFC	Design for Change Spain
HIDE	Hidepark Civic Association Triptych
ISIM	isIMPACT
KQ	Kalniciema Quarter
LABORELEC	Engie Laborelec
LCREA	Lucca Crea
LUCCA	Comune di Lucca
NITRA	Mesto Nitra
PUJ	Pontificia Universidad Javeriana
RIGA	Riga Planning Region

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SUA	Slovak University of Agriculture in Nitra
TSR	Tesseract
UCO	University of Cordoba
UNIFI	Università di Pisa
UREAD	University of Reading
WTG	WellnessTechGroup

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document represents **an overview of the available items and tools referring to D 8.4. City Communication Pack** of the INclusive Health And wellBeing In small and medium size ciTies (IN-HABIT) project, WP8 Dissemination, Communication and Outreach. It includes all the available visual and digital tools, shared with the Local Community Activators (LCAs) of the participating cities and the Key Local Contacts (KLCs) in charge of communication actions. The tools have been developed after a thorough discussion with the above-mentioned teams, to guarantee a simple, user-friendly, and effective use during local communication and dissemination activities and events.

The communication strategy is tightly coupled with the dissemination activities, given that the focus from the start will be on **creating awareness** by publicising the project in the cities and beyond. To multiply the impact and adapt the communication efforts, partners will use their local media and own communication channels to **disseminate project results** and **engage with local actors**. Each partner is responsible for identifying local stakeholders in its city/country and ensuring that the project communication reaches the largest possible number of targeted actors at a local level. Other city and international levels will be also targeted through city networks and relevant events.

An initial version of the D 8.4 is issued in M16 and will be a living document that will evolve during the project's lifetime. As local communication initiatives are held, and communication necessities emerge, other specific tools will be added to the package and shared with the Project Partners. The package will be stored in the internal repository of IN-HABIT documents, ensuring access to all partners.

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SCENARIO

The IN-HABIT project was born in a year characterised by many changes that have **revolutionised** the uses, the possibilities of communication and social interaction and the working methods, impacting the ability of some events to have a prominent offline event capable of generating exchange, affection, interaction, and networking. The regulation resulting from the need to stem the COVID-19 pandemic has **prevented demonstrations and events** around the world from taking place, including the most important and symbolic ones. To date, it is not yet clear what will happen in the near future and if this will allow us to return to the previous meeting and communication habits. The unpredictability of events due to COVID-19 impacts the IN-HABIT project because it makes it more difficult to understand whether the physical events, which have objectives linked to the fundamental mission of the project (promoting inclusion, wellbeing), will be able to take place. In this phase of the project, however, it is important to be able to plan the organisation of such events. For this reason, to make planning more linear, **a more digital approach to events** is proposed.

Addressing a critical scenario all together also requires an extension of responsibility: with the help of LCAs first, and then Local Observers (LOs), it is expected that the project will be able to propose communication activities and **enable the use of digital channels. These events** would participate in **achieving the objective of inclusion** in the project but also in the long term for categories at risk of exclusion/disadvantage.

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1. Communications objectives and field of action

The tools included in this deliverable aim to contribute to the **effective communication** of the project and its results, engaging internal and external targets. The IN-HABIT project aims to craft a future based on **high quality, multifunctional, public spaces** able to integrate digital, social, cultural and nature-based innovation to **enhance health and wellbeing**, while ensuring 'the right to the city' as specified in the UN's Habitat III New Urban agenda (adopted at the United Nations Conference on Housing and Sustainable Urban Development, Habitat III, in Quito, Ecuador, on 20 October 2016, and endorsed by the United Nations General Assembly at its sixty-eighth plenary meeting of the seventy-first session on 23 December 2016).

At the end of the project, several multifunctional urban public spaces will be regenerated: **green, sustainable and creative areas** in the *patios* of Las Palmeras, a deprived neighbourhood in Cordoba, uniting it with Axerquia, a city centre neighbourhood, whose *patios* are recognised as UNESCO Intangible Culture Heritage sites; a **food market area** in the Āgenskalns district of Riga; two urban **parks** reorganised to support human-animal interactions in Lucca; a **multifunctional cycling corridor** in Nitra. The quality of these urban spaces will improve Inclusive Health and Wellbeing (IHW) in terms of green space availability, safety, accessibility, resilience, and inclusiveness, increasing the capacity to respond to mobility, recreational, security and socio-economic needs of groups at risk of marginalisation and exclusion. The deployment of visionary and integrated solutions (VIS) will thus **enhance liveability** of these public spaces for local inhabitants.

These agendas put the focus on **the role of cities** in addressing systemic global challenges and their relevance in managing the transition towards sustainable development. IN-HABIT will offer **sound evidence-based results** and **best practices** on the role of public spaces to boost IHW in European SMSCs.

In a local, cities and neighbourhood-related environment, the project purposes might be:

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- Locally, the IN-HABIT project can mean a significant increase of visibility, especially in touristic areas. In addition, feeling part of a European and prestigious partnership.
- Local stakeholders that replicate the model of best practices in IHW proposed by the IN-HABIT project have a great opportunity to increase their own visibility and awareness raising capacity and options to act as ambassadors of sustainable practices in IHW.
- The rebuilt public spaces will be inspirational for many other areas in the world facing similar problems, when addressing GDEI based co-design, co-deployment, and co-management in different urban contexts .
- Proposed visionary solutions will promote sustainable urban mobility patterns and sustainable physical and social connections among city areas, decrease spatial and social segregation and promote healthier diet and lifestyles, cultural life, and livelihood opportunities in peripheral districts.

The general communication campaign of IN-HABIT has started in M12, September 2021, and the cities have now started to focus on more local communication activities such as the local launches.

This choice takes into consideration the need of cities to organise the establishment of the IN-HUBs and of the project itself according to the time needed for each one. The first communication campaign was a **general presentation campaign** for the project. Following this, it is expected that the four cities, once the IN-HUBs establishment has been set up, will be ready to take action for a **public presentation at a local level**, aimed at gathering the maximum visibility and consensus from local targets for the first time.

In this framework, all the necessary tools have been provided to the PPs in the previous months, in particular referring to communication guidelines, visual identity package and items, and trainings. This **City Communication Pack** integrates the already available tools, allowing user-friendly items for the local communicators to adapt to their necessities and to use on the local

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field of action. Furthermore, regular meetings with the LCAs and KLCs are being held from May 2021 to discuss operational matters in communication, applied to local contexts.

2. City communication pack tools

The items contained in the pack have been designed following the suggestions and requests of LCAs and KLCs and **all include**:

- specific layout instructions on how to print/produce such materials locally
- .ai versions, editable
- .pdf versions, printable
- layout characteristics (dimensions, materials, etc.) to be ready to produce

More specific tools will be developed in the upcoming months, in particular:

- a *project brochure*, highlighting the research and innovation aspects of the project. This brochure will be made available once the first collected data are analysed, and an ad hoc connection has already been established with the project research partners to communicate scientific information to the public.
- *promotional items at a local level and in local languages*, in particularly those designed after completing the stakeholders' mapping for each city (i.e., window stickers for the places supporting the project initiatives).
- updated project leaflets and invitation *templates* in the four local languages, according to the cities' needs in correspondence with local events.
- *Logbook of activities* – in the four languages, to support the cities' reporting of activities and experiences on the field.
- *Explanation sheet* for the consent forms, reporting an easy and user-friendly explanation of the informed consents

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As anticipated, the following tools will be subject to integration and updates as local communication specific necessities emerge and are shared.

2.1 Project leaflets

An extended project leaflet is available in English (A4 format), and four locally focused leaflets (A4 format, foldable) are available in local languages at the following links:

English_

<https://www.inhabit-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/INHABIT-LEAFLET-WEB2.pdf>

Spanish_Cordoba

<https://www.inhabit-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/INHABIT-LEAFLET-CORDOBA.pdf>

Italian_Lucca

<http://www.inhabit-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/INHABIT-LEAFLET-LUCCA.pdf>

Latvian_Riga

<http://www.inhabit-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/INHABIT-LEAFLET-RIGA.pdf>

Slovak_Nitra

<http://www.inhabit-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/INHABIT-LEAFLET-NITRA.pdf>

Printable versions are available on the project internal repository. Each of them has been designed for a black/white or colour printing.

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THE PROJECT

Inclusive Health And wellBeing in small and medium size cities (IN-HABIT) is an EU Horizon 2020 project that aims to identify visionary and integrated solutions to promote inclusive health and wellbeing in small and medium size cities. In each of the four pilot cities, the project will investigate how the mobilisation of existing underused resources, such as culture and heritage, food, human-animal bonds and art and environment might contribute to boost health and wellbeing, with a focus on gender, diversity, equity and inclusion. The integrated approach will combine technological, digital, nature-based, cultural, and social innovations in selected urban public spaces. These solutions will be co-design, co-developed and co-managed with local inhabitants and stakeholders. The project will be implemented during a five-year period (2020-2025).

THE TEAM

The IN-HABIT consortium is a multidisciplinary team of 21 partners from 7 European countries (Spain, Italy, Latvia, Slovakia, United Kingdom, Germany, Belgium) and Colombia. The team is composed of universities, high-level research organisations, city representatives, grass-roots partners, small or medium-sized enterprises, and non-profit organisations, all working together towards a common goal.

- University of Córdoba
- Ayuntamiento de Córdoba
- Neighbourhood Association of Las Palmeras
- Baltic Studies Centre
- Riga Planning Region
- Kalnciema Quarter
- University of Pisa
- Comune di Lucca
- Lucca Crea
- Slovak University of Agriculture
- Mesto Nitra
- Hidepark Civic Association Triptch
- University of Reading
- iMPACT
- Tesserae
- Bridge for Billions
- Design for Change Spain
- Book on a Tree
- Engie Laborelec
- Wellness TechGroup
- Pontificia Universidad Javeriana

THE OBJECTIVES

IN-HABIT, over its five-year duration, will strive to meet the following specific objectives with the overall aim of fostering inclusive health and wellbeing in small and medium size cities:

To make urban public spaces safer, more accessible and more inclusive.

To develop an inclusive urban planning framework focusing on gender, diversity, equity and inclusion aspects.

To promote healthy behaviors and increase the wellbeing of inhabitants in selected neighbourhoods.

To develop new ways of measuring the impact of actions on health and wellbeing, using an inclusive approach.

To create IN-HUBs in each city: innovative interaction spaces whose objective is to design and implement collaborative neighbourhood development measures through public, private, people partnerships.

To share knowledge of the visionary and integrated solutions, successfully deployed in each city, for replication in other places.

THE CITIES

The IN-HABIT project is focusing on four peripheral small and medium size cities in Europe: Riga (Latvia), Córdoba (Spain), Lucca (Italy), and Nitra (Slovakia). IN-HABIT's actions in each city aim to foster inclusive health and wellbeing by integrating innovative solutions around four main values: Heritage & Culture; Food, Animal-Human Bonds; Art & Environment.

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Fig. 1 - General leaflet

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Fig. 2 - Local leaflets

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2.2 Project roll - ups

In 4 local versions, one for each city. Characteristics: material 500 gr/square mt (PVC), with structure, 85x 200 cm.

Fig. 3 - Roll ups/Banners

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2.3 Project presentation

A project presentation, in English, for external audiences, has been made available to PPs on the internal repository and is subject to revisions and updates.

2.4 Project promo items

Stickers, following versions:

1. **reel** in five versions: 4 colours background with white logo, white background with coloured logo
2. **sheet**, A4 format, white background with coloured logo

Characteristics: no finishing, orientation on sheet 0 ° exit direction, circular format diameter 5 cm, quantity 200/each.

Pins, following versions: 4 colours (one for each city), white with colour logo, dark blue/white logo.

Characteristics: 2,5 cm diameter

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Fig. 4 - Stickers

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Fig. 5 - Pins

3. Further explorations and timeline

The virtual environment of the project is affected by the **habits of use** and access to different channels at different times of the day and in the lives of inhabitants.

Local communicators, being them both LCAs and KLCs, then, will have to be proactive in bringing the institutional communication of the project onto those channels used and

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disseminated at the local level, taking into consideration the **different local targets** that may not all have the same interest or access to certain channels.

Consideration of the virtual context in which engagement can take place must be **holistic** with an open and broad approach and effective in its considering all the possible communication options. This approach was a starting point for the training work carried out with LCAs and KLCs and interpreted as a baseline for the local specific addendum to communication guidelines.

Further materials to be developed might include:

- posters for public spaces usage
- cards, postcards, shopping lists or calendars
- promotional materials such as gadgets (bags, etc.)
- flyers

This material is available in a communication toolkit for internal usage for the local stakeholders and everyone participating in the project, including relevant guidelines and materials for communication and is subject to updates as new information and necessities emerge.

Annexes

Annex 1. IN-HABIT Visual identity, project templates and graphic package

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OUR LOGO

The multi-coloured logo is the primary brand mark for IN-HABIT. In the following pages, you'll learn how the logo can be used to ensure consistency across all touchpoints.

[Download the IN-HABIT logos: https://bit.ly/3cpodwL](https://bit.ly/3cpodwL)

The dark blue logo is the correct logo for formal situations of the IN-HABIT identity.

[Download the IN-HABIT logos: https://bit.ly/3cpodwL](https://bit.ly/3cpodwL)

In addition to the primary and secondary logos, the following colourways can also be used for the logo.

[Download the IN-HABIT logos: https://bit.ly/3cpodwL](https://bit.ly/3cpodwL)

LIGHT BLUE

RED

YELLOW

GREEN

BLACK

WHITE

The protected area keeps the IN-HABIT logo free from other text or graphic elements that could compromise its legibility or recognition. The height of the H from the IN-HABIT logo should be used to define the protected area around the margins.

Coloured versions of the IN-HABIT logo should **not** be used over a coloured background or image. In these situations, use the white version.

COLOUR BACKGROUND

The white version of the IN-HABIT logo must be used over a coloured background.

IMAGE BACKGROUND

The white version of the IN-HABIT logo must be used over images.

Example of incorrect use of the primary logo over an image

Below are some IN-HABIT logo application examples that follow the rules set out on the previous page.

POWERPOINT DOCUMENT

Example of the primary IN-HABIT logo being used in a PowerPoint document

WORD DOCUMENT

Example of the primary IN-HABIT logo being used in the header of a Word document

SOCIAL MEDIA ASSET

Example of the white IN-HABIT logo being used over an image for use on social media

Below are some violations of the brand guidelines.
Note: these examples don't cover all possible violations.

Do **not** stretch or distort the logo

Do **not** apply a different colour to the logo to those described in this chapter

Do **not** change the position of any of the logo's elements

Do **not** overlay graphic elements or text over the logo

Do **not** use a gradient background that compromises the logo's legibility

Do **not** apply a gradient to the logo

Do **not** apply a drop shadow to the logo

Do **not** recreate the primary logo in grayscale

IN-HABIT is co-funded by the Horizon 2020 programme of the European Union and, where appropriate, this should be communicated on brand material via the EU flag and associated copy below. There are two versions:

[Download the EU flag graphics: https://bit.ly/3cpodwL](https://bit.ly/3cpodwL)

[Read the EU communication toolkit: https://bit.ly/2NGdeER](https://bit.ly/2NGdeER)

CO-FUNDED (WHITE BACKGROUND)

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GRANT (WHITE BACKGROUND)

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CO-FUNDED (COLOURED BACKGROUND OR IMAGE)

Co-funded by the Horizon 2020 programme of the European Union

GRANT (COLOURED BACKGROUND OR IMAGE)

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The EU flag and accompanying text can be used over photography where there is enough reasonable contrast between the text and the image to make the text legible.

The EU flag and accompanying text should be used over a brand colour when overlaying over photography where there is **not** enough contrast between the text and the image to make the text legible.

The EU flag and accompanying text should **not** be used over photography where there is not enough contrast between the text and the image to make the text legible.

The EU flag and accompanying text should be displayed in all IN-HABIT brand documents such as PowerPoint presentations and Word documents.

POWERPOINT DOCUMENT

The EU flag features at the bottom of each PowerPoint slide

WORD DOCUMENT

The EU flag features in the footer on every page of a Word document

OUR COLOURS

The IN-HABIT primary colours should be the dominant colours used throughout IN-HABIT material. IN-HABIT Formal Blue should be used in formal situations and applications of the IN-HABIT identity.

The CMYK colour values should be used for print applications. The RGB colour values should be used for digital applications. The HEX colour values should be used for web-based applications. Note, the CMYK colours used in print applications will look different compared to the RGB colours used digitally.

IN-HABIT BLUE

CMYK 78 24 0 8
 RGB 36 173 234
 HEX #24ADEA

IN-HABIT RED

CMYK 0 85 92 0
 RGB 239 68 65
 HEX #EF4441

IN-HABIT YELLOW

CMYK 00 00 00 00
 RGB 249 203 88
 HEX #F9CB58

IN-HABIT GREEN

CMYK 60 0 63 0
 RGB 53 229 149
 HEX #35E595

IN-HABIT FORMAL BLUE

CMYK 70 33 0 57
 RGB 33 73 109
 HEX #21496D

BLACK

CMYK 40 40 40 100
 RGB 0 0 0
 HEX #000000

WHITE

CMYK 0 0 0 0
 RGB 255 255 255
 HEX #FFFFFF

The IN-HABIT secondary colours are used for the IN-HABIT brand icons and can also be used as accent colours across various IN-HABIT material.

The CMYK colour values should be used for print applications. The RGB colour values should be used for digital applications. The HEX colour values should be used for web-based applications. Note, the CMYK colours used in print applications will look different compared to the RGB colours used digitally.

LIGHT BLUE

CMYK 83 42 0 0
 RGB 0 126 198
 HEX #007EC6

LIGHT RED

CMYK 9 100 46 2
 RGB 213 2 83
 HEX #D50253

LIGHT YELLOW

CMYK 0 44 71 0
 RGB 249 164 84
 HEX #F9A454

LIGHT GREEN

CMYK 69 0 69 0
 RGB 6 211 122
 HEX #06D37A

DARK BLUE

CMYK 100 86 39 30
 RGB 2 42 90
 HEX #022A5A

DARK RED

CMYK 0 82 51 0
 RGB 249 75 92
 HEX #F94B5C

DARK YELLOW

CMYK 0 67 94 0
 RGB 255 109 1
 HEX #FF6D01

DARK GREEN

CMYK 91 36 100 34
 RGB 0 91 35
 HEX #005B23

Each city has a primary IN-HABIT brand colour assigned to it based on the dominant colour of the country's flag. This should be the dominant colour use for any city-specific material (for example, backgrounds of text boxes and accent colour).

NITRA (SLOVAKIA)

LIGHT BLUE

RIGA (LATVIA)

RED

CORDOBA (SPAIN)

YELLOW

LUCCA (ITALY)

GREEN

OUR TYPOGRAPHY

The primary typeface for all IN-HABIT materials is Nunito. Where it's not possible to use Nunito, Calibri should be used. Note: Nunito and Calibri should **never** be used together in any application.

[Download the Nunito brand fonts: https://bit.ly/3cpodwL](https://bit.ly/3cpodwL)

PRIMARY TYPEFACE

NUNITO

REGULAR

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789

BOLD

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789

FALLBACK TYPEFACE

CALIBRI

REGULAR

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789

BOLD

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789

Nunito Bold should always be used for titles and short bits of text that need to stand out. Nunito Regular should always be used for body copy. The same applies to Calibri, if Nunito can't be used.

TITLE TEXT

Titles should be set in **all caps** and **bold** weight.

Body text

Body text should be set in **sentence case** and **regular** weight.

The slide features a blue header with the 'IN-HABIT' logo in the top left corner. The main content area is white with a large, faint, light-blue abstract graphic of interconnected circles and lines on the right side. The text is arranged as follows:

- TITLE GOES HERE** (in all caps and bold weight)
- Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Praesent tortor lectus, laoreet a laoreet ac, vulputate id libero. Nunc nulla nunc, blandit nec sem a, consectetur venenatis nisi. Integer sit amet tempus nibh. Suspendisse ac condimentum libero. Nunc hendrerit mi ac aliquam posuere.

At the bottom left, there is a small European Union logo and text: "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 695227". The number "3" is in the bottom right corner.

Example PowerPoint presentation slide

OUR ICONS

We have a suite of brand icons that can be used to help illustrate and visualise information throughout the various brand applications.

🔗 **Download the brand icons:** <https://bit.ly/3cpodwL>

Note, we have a suite of brand icons available in a PowerPoint template for immediate use.

The brand icons are available to use in the following brand colours.

BLUE

RED

YELLOW

GREEN

BLACK

WHITE

The icon(s) can be any of the brand colours stated on the previous page (except for white) when used on a white background.

The icon(s) should always be white when used over a coloured background and image.

Example of an icon being used in a PowerPoint presentation

Example of icons being used in a PowerPoint presentation

OUR PATTERN

Our brand pattern can be used across various brand applications.

[Download the brand patterns: https://bit.ly/3cpodwL](https://bit.ly/3cpodwL)

MULTICOLOURED PATTERN

YELLOW

GREEN

RED

LIGHT BLUE

DARK BLUE

Our brand pattern can be used as a background across various brand applications.

PATTERN USE

Example of the multicoloured pattern being used in a PowerPoint presentation

Where text is laid over the top of a pattern, a text box in one of the brand colours must be used with white text.

Don't overlay text over the brand pattern without a coloured text box behind the text

Similarly, the graphic that makes up the pattern can be used on its own as a background across various brand applications.

GRAPHIC USE

Example of the graphic being used in a PowerPoint presentation

The graphic can also be used at 10% opacity of any of the brand colours.

Don't use a text colour that doesn't have reasonable contrast with the pattern or graphic colour behind it

OUR IMAGES

Along with the use of the brand colours and icons, image use is an integral part of the IN-HABIT brand identity. Images can convey a message or a mood within the overall IN-HABIT brand and should focus on people or places.

[Download brand images: https://bit.ly/3cpodwL](https://bit.ly/3cpodwL)

Where high-quality stock imagery use isn't possible, "home made" imagery use is allowed where the image is authentic and personable.

Generic stock images that aren't authentic shouldn't be used.

Images can be used standalone or paired with text as a background. If pairing with text, the text must always be clearly legible.

Where images are used for backgrounds with text laid over the top, a text box in one of the brand colours must be used with white text.

Example of an image being used in a PowerPoint presentation

BRAND APPLICATIONS

The IN-HABIT visual identity and graphic package includes:

VISUAL GUIDELINES

A simple tool with examples on how to use logos and imagery, along with dos and don'ts. This how-to guide will help creating consistent projects in line with the IN-HABIT brand.

OUR LOGOS

Our logos in the colours of the project palette, and black and white; both in high and low resolution.

OUR ICONS

Our icons in the colours of the project palette, and black and white; both in high and low resolution.

OUR PATTERN

Our patterns to be used as background designs for your communication.

NUNITO

OUR TYPOGRAPHY

Our typeface/font.

EU FLAG

The EU flag both in colour and black and white, including the project funding information.

IMAGES

Free images for you to use on your presentations.

The IN-HABIT visual identity and graphic package includes templates in the following formats:

DOCUMENT TEMPLATES

- Press release
- Report
- Meeting agenda
- Meeting minutes
- Deliverable
- Letterhead
- Simple text (free form)

Available in two formats:

- Microsoft Word: downloadable for offline work.
- Google Drive: for documents requiring contribution from many partners. By reducing the number of saved versions, we reduce the potential for errors.

PRESENTATION TEMPLATES

- Formal presentation (for example, for external meetings, conferences, etc.)
- Informal presentation (for internal meetings, etc.)

Available in two formats:

- Lighter version, for download
- Complete version, for online use (like Teams, Drive or other collaborative spaces)
- Icon library (separated - for easier, lighter use)

All templates have been tested and work correctly across several devices. In the folder, you will also find a “how to” guide showing how to add icons, etc. to these templates.

Media-rich presentations are an effective way to connect with your audience. Including high-quality images often adds hugely to audience engagement, but it also increases file size. That means your presentation or file could be too large for some email servers, and it could run a lot slower on some computers.

POWERPOINT DOCUMENT

To reduce image size in Microsoft PowerPoint:

1. Select a picture, go to the “**Format**” tab and select “**Picture Tools**”.
2. Choose “**Compress Pictures**” in the top left corner. A pop-up box will display your resolution options. For most online purposes, a resolution of 150ppi is fine. If you’re going to print your presentation, choose the print 220ppi option. You can reduce the file size of all images in your presentation by selecting “**Apply to all pictures in the file**”.

Select ‘On-screen (150 ppi)’ picture quality for online purposes

By reducing the resolution of your images your image file sizes are limited, which means your presentation is no larger than it needs to be.

If you’re sending a document by email, convert your presentations into PDF format and use versions with reduced image resolution.

WORD DOCUMENT

To reduce image size in Microsoft Word:

1. Go to the “**File**” tab and select “**Reduce File Size**”.
2. In the pop-up box, select the resolution. For digital, use 150ppi and for printing, use 220ppi. You can reduce the file size of all images in your presentation by selecting “**Apply to all pictures in the file**”.

Select ‘Print (220 ppi)’ picture quality for print purposes

The IN-HABIT primary logo should always be used in Word documents.

 Download Word templates: <https://bit.ly/3cpodwL>

The IN-HABIT logo should be present in the top-left corner of every slide. The primary logo should always be used when the background is white. The white logo should always be used over a coloured background or image.

Download PowerPoint templates: <https://bit.ly/3cpodwL>

The white IN-HABIT logo can be used in the top-left corner of photography-based social media assets. The white logo should always be used over a coloured background or image.

When used over white, as in a title bar, the primary logo should be used. When used over an image, use the white logo.

[Visit the IN-HABIT website: https://www.inhabit-h2020.eu/](https://www.inhabit-h2020.eu/)

The roll up designs should follow the visual guidelines with the IN-HABIT logo always placed in the top half and the EU flag and accompanying copy placed at the bottom.

An example of a roll up design using photography

An example of a formal roll up design

Brochure design should follow the visual guidelines. Photography should be used in brochures only if the brochure will be professionally printed; otherwise, a single-coloured pattern should be used.

Below: An example of a brochure design using our brand pattern

Above: An example of a brochure design using photography

